

The Influence of Price Perception, Promotion, Product Perception and Brand Image on Repurchase Intention of Krisbow Products through Customer Satisfaction as a Mediation Variable

Satrio Panji Anggolo¹ Achmad Fachrodji ²

¹ Master of Management, ² Lecturer of Postgraduate,
Universitas Mercu Buana Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- This research aims to analyze Factors that influence Repurchase Intention include: Price Perception, Promotion, Perception Product, Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction. This research also wants to analyze influence Price Perception, Promotion, Perception Product, Brand Image on Repurchase Intention as well analyze how Customer Satisfaction mediates influence Price Perception, Promotion, Perception Product, Brand Image on Repurchase Intention. Population in this research consumers who have buy product Krisbow at the Krisbow Shop Tangerang branch . Samples used as many as 175 respondents. Samples used as many as 175 customers Krisbow Tangerang branch with use hair theory et., al that is amount indicator times 5-10. Retrieval technique sample used is simple random sampling technique was used in a way random without Pay attention to strata in the population the. Research methods usedis quantitative with SEM-PLS. Based on analysis in this research was obtained results that : Price perception has an influence significant towards Customer Satisfaction; Promotion influential positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction; Perception Product No influential towards Customer Satisfaction; Brand Image is influential positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction; Customer Satisfaction has an effect positive and significant on Repurchase Intention; Price no influential on Repurchase Intention; Promotion No influential on Repurchase Intention; Perception Product influential positive and significant on Repurchase Intention; Brand Image does not influential on Repurchase Intention; Customer Satisfaction works mediate the influence of Price, Promotion, Brand Image on Repurchase Intention; Customer Satisfaction does not succeed mediate influence Perception Product on Repurchase Intention.

Keywords:- Price Perception, Promotion, Perception Product, Brand Image, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Marketing is one of from activities the main things that entrepreneurs do in his efforts to defend continuity his life , to develop and gain profit (Priangani 2013). A company said succeed operate its function if capable sell products to consumers and obtain maximum profits possible (Stone et al. 2020). Consumer as one of the element, holding role important Where from time to time they the more critical in respond something product. Something change paradigm more marketing driven by change situation and condition public globaly. Change the covers increasing market share chosen, loyalty increasing customersdevelop, develop public information, developments channel distribution development method new in shopping and paying, changes pattern consumption family cause consumer own depending on the increasing power increase along with current development.

Development business in Indonesia lately it's been getting longer and longer strict will competition, change and uncertainty (Afrilita T 2013). This situation gives rise to sharp competition between company, fine Because increasingly competitors increases, the volume of product increases increases, as well increase rapidly technology. This is compelling companies to pay more attention possible environment influence company, company order know marketing strategies like what and how should be applied in company. Therefore competition is very important for success or failure something company (Imon et al. 2018). So that company have to be more careful read as well as anticipate market conditions so can create quality products, deliver quality service is possible satisfying consumer so that can win competition.

The more increase producer or company offering goods in form products and services, then the more Consumers also have many choices when determine So or not buy (Budi 2014). According to Hikmayanti et al. (2016) retrieval process decision purchase indicated involvement perceived consumers important as well as interest consumer to acquisition, consumption and disposition goods, services or idea.

One of most dynamic industry currently, owner retail businesses, especially those based shop (store basedretailing), must capable anticipate changes that occur in the market and with responsive adapt it to business they so that always in accordance with life style (Utomo 2016). Consumer make Lots decision purchase every days, and decisions purchase is point focus from effort marketer. Most company big want to know what to be factor decider decision purchase consumer.

In this research the object was chosen is PT Krisbow Indonesia which was founded in 2013 as provider various product quality start from tools hand and electrical , machinery, equipment cleanliness and safety work,

generator, up to equipment House stairs for sale in a way exclusive through Krisbow Store and all network Kawan Lama Group distributor. As equipment companies and distributors industry The largest in Indonesia which currently has 65 stores spread across throughout Indonesia and has more than 10,000 product items with service center, service full sell and dealers who have spread across various regions in Indonesia as well as some countries in Southeast Asia are currently being offered to customers who need it need that and ready compete with company company others in Indonesia are good from company domestically or company especially abroad formerly has exist in Indonesia.

Fig. 1: Sales Data Product Krisbow 2022

From Figure 1, you can seen that sale product Krisbow at the Tangerang branch in 2022 experienced increase and decrease in each month, which is March until June experience decline sale However slowly return increased in the following month. Therefore, researchers

want to do research to find out on base what are the consumers buy product krisbow.

To know influencing factors interest purchase come back, writer try do pre survey research . The following is the result data pre - survey research conducted on customers Krisbow totaling 30 respondents.

Table 1: Pre Results Survey Researcher

Variabel	Persentase
Persepsi Harga	56.7%
Trend	16.7%
Brand	63.3%
Persepsi Kualitas	56.7%
Packaging	16.7%
Promosi	60%
Warna	20%
Atribut Produk	40%

From the picture presurvey results above obtained results Where from amount respondents as many as 30 people, and for those who choose perception price (56.7%), Brand (63.3%), Perception Quality (56.7%), Promotion (60%), Trend (16.7%), Attributes Product (40%), Color (20%) and Packaging (16.7%). With results pre -survey this researcher want to retrieves 4 results top to decide variable,

where results the obtained for the variable Price Perception, Brand, Perception Quality, and also Promotion.

Based on background back above researcher want to develop existing research with take a number of variable and reinforced with results from pre- survey, that is researcher want to know about influence Price Perception,

Perception Quality, Promotion and Brand Image, against satisfaction influencing customers decision purchase Krisbow products are back.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Customer Satisfaction

Activity marketing carried out by marketers with communicate and offer goods or service from his company is to create A satisfaction for his customers. According to Kotler and Keller (2018) customer satisfaction is 'a product received performance (or outcome) in relation to the person's expectations'. Feeling like or disappointed somebody as results from comparison between performance or perceived and expected products.

According to Fandy (2016) satisfaction consumer is evaluation post-purchase between perception to performance alternative product or selected services fulfil or hope, if perception to performance No Can fulfil hope, then what happens is dissatisfaction. One of determining factor satisfaction customer is perception customer . Understanding satisfaction consumer according to Ali Hasan (2018:150) satisfaction consumer is feeling like or disappointment emerged after compare performance (results) of the product in mind to expected performance (results).

Customer Satisfaction Indicators According to Daryanto and Ismanto (2014), namely 1)Quality Product; 2) Factor Emotional ; 3) Cost and convenience.

B. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase intention according to Hellier et al (2015) is "Repurchase intention is the individual's judgment about buying again a designated service from the same company, taking into account his or her current situation and likely circumstances" Intention purchase return is consideration individual to buy return designated service from the same company, with consider situation current and possible circumstances happen. Repurchase Intention according to Peter & Olson (2000) is a purchasing activity that is carried out more than once or several times. The satisfaction that a consumer gets can encourage someone to make repeat purchases, become loyal to the product or loyal to the place where he bought the item so that the consumer can tell good things to other people.

According to Thamrin and Tantri (2019) repurchase interest is purchase interest that is based on or purchasing experiences that have been made in the past. High repurchase interest reflects a high level of satisfaction from consumers when deciding to adopt a product. The decision to adopt or reject a product arises after consumers try the product and then develop feelings of liking or disliking the product. A feeling of liking for a product arises when consumers have the perception that the product they use is of good quality and can fulfill or even fulfill the consumer's desires and expectations.

Repurchase Intention indicators are 1) Transactional Interest; 2) Referential Interest; and 3) Preferential Interest.

C. Price Perception

Definition product according to Fandy (2016) is understanding subjective producer over ' something ' that can offered as effort to achieve objective organization through fulfillment needs and desires consumer, accordingly with competition and capacity organization as well as Power buy market. Consumers will favor products that offer the best quality, performance and innovative accessories. A quality product is a product that is able to provide results that are more than expected. Kotler (2016) defines perceived quality as the overall characteristics and properties of goods and services that influence the ability to meet stated or implied needs.

Kotler (2016) emphasizes one thing that must always be remembered, namely that perceived quality is the perception of customers, therefore perceived quality cannot be determined objectively. In addition, customer perceptions will involve what is important to customers because each customer has different interests in a product or service (Sagala 2019). So it can be said that discussing perceived quality means discussing customer involvement and interests. High perceived quality indicates that through long-term use, consumers gain differentiation and superiority from the brand. Rivai and Wahyudi (2017) identified perceived quality as a component of brand value where high perceived quality will direct consumers to choose the brand compared to competing brands. The perceived quality felt by consumers influences the consumer's willingness to buy a product. This means that the higher the value perceived by consumers, the higher the consumer's willingness to ultimately buy.

According to Kumbara (2021), price perception is the view or perception of price, how customers view a particular price (high, low, reasonable) has a strong influence on purchase intention and purchase satisfaction. According to Dewi and Wibowo (2018), perception price is cost relative must expended to obtain product or the services he provides want . Perception about price be measured based on perception customer namely with method ask to customer variables whatever you think is most important in choose A product.

According to (2015), perception price often identified with perception quality and perception costs incurred to obtain product. Perception price formed by two dimensions main, i.e perception quality and perception cost.

According to Muharam and Solih (2017) perception price can be measured through a number of consisting of indicators from 1) Conformity price with quality product; 2) Conformity price with benefit; and 3) Competitive price.

D. Promotion

Promotion can be defined as the best combination of strategies from variables like advertising, personal selling and other promotional tools, all of them planned to achieve sales program objectives (Kotler and Armstrong 2016), whereas according to Fandy and Gregorius (2016) in essence promotion is something from communication marketing in question with communication marketing is activity marketing effort spread information, influence / persuade and remind the target market on company and its products to be ready accept, buy and be loyal to the products offered by the company concerned.

Promotion is a campaign marketing designed for stimulating faster purchases or bigger on product or service by consumers (Kotler and Keller 2018). Promotion is one of the factors that determines the success of a marketing program. No matter how high-quality the product is, if consumers have never heard of it and are not sure that the product will be useful for consumers. Promotion sale is a promotional program retail in frame push happen sale or to improve sales (Fitra 2017). Promotion in form whatever is something attempt to influence party other. More specifically, promotion is one of the elements of marketing mix (Darul and Lampung 2021). Promotion as a mechanism communication marketing, exchange information between buyers and sellers.

Indicator promotion according to Rachmawati and Patrikha (2021) promotion can be measured through a number of indicators from 1) Advertising; 2) Promotion sale; 3) Personal selling; and 4) Direct marketing.

E. Product Perception

Definition product according to Fandy (2016) is understanding subjective producer over 'something' that can be offered as effort to achieve objective organization through fulfillment needs and desires consumer, accordingly with competition and capacity organization as well as Power buy market. Consumers will favor products that offer the best quality, performance and innovative accessories. A quality product is a product that is able to provide results that are more than expected. Kotler (2016) defines perceived quality as the overall characteristics and properties of goods and services that influence the ability to meet stated or implied needs.

Kotler (2016) emphasizes one thing that must always be remembered, namely that perceived quality is the perception of customers, therefore perceived quality cannot be determined objectively. In addition, customer perceptions will involve what is important to customers because each customer has different interests in a product or service (Sagala 2019). So it can be said that discussing perceived quality means discussing customer involvement and interests. High perceived quality indicates that through long-term use, consumers gain differentiation and superiority from the brand. Rivai and Wahyudi (2017) identified perceived quality as a component of brand value where high perceived quality will direct consumers to choose the brand compared to competing brands. The perceived quality felt by consumers influences the consumer's willingness to buy a product. This means that the higher the value perceived by consumers, the higher the consumer's willingness to ultimately buy.

Product Perception Indicators According to (2015) to determine product quality, indicators can be used including: 1) Conformity of quality and benefits received; 2) Product Information; and 3) Competitive quality.

F. Brand Image

According to Swasty (2016) brand is "dimension product or services that differentiate it in a number of methods from product or other services designed to fulfill the same needs". These differences may be functional, rational, or real relating to the performance of a brand's products. Brands can also be more symbolic, emotional, or intangible related to what the brand represents or what it means in a more abstract sense.

According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2015), brand image is a perception that lasts a long time, is formed through experience, and is relatively consistent. Therefore, consumer attitudes and actions towards a brand image are one of the important elements that encourage consumers to buy a product. According to Supriyadi et al. (2016) brand image is the consumer's desire to think, feel and act towards a brand.

Brand Image Indicators According to Audiah (2019), namely: 1) Company image (corporate image); 2) Consumer image (user image); and 3) Product image.

Based on theories the so framework thinking in this research as follows:

Fig 3: Framework Thinking

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses method quantitative with Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS SEM) approach. Statistical tools used for testing hypotheses _This research is a Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) program. Data will analyzed with two models. Measurement Model (Outer Model) is a connecting measurement model indicator with variable latent. Structural Model (Inner Model) is a structural model that connects between latent variable.

The variables used in this research is Perception price (X1), Promotion (X2), Perception product (X3), Brand Image (X4), Customer satisfaction (Y1), and Repurchase Intention (Y2). The data collection technique in this research is non - probability sampling using purposive sampling. A questionnaire with a Likert scale will be given

to consumers who have purchased Krisbow products at the Tangerang branch of the Krisbow Shop. The sample used was 175 customers of the Tangerang branch of Krisbow using the hair et al theory, namely the number of indicators multiplied by 5-10. The sampling technique used was a simple random sampling technique which was carried out randomly without paying attention to the strata of the population.

IV. RESULTS

A. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

This model defines How every indicator relate with variable its latency, or can said that the outer model can specify connection between latent variable with the indicators. The outer model is carried out by looking at the values of convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability.

Fig. 4: Path Diagram Outer Loading

➤ Test result Convergent Validity

Testing Convergent Validity is the loading factor value on the latent variable with the indicators. This measurement is carried out to test validity of each variable. Data is said to be valid if obtain loading value > 0.7. Based on the path diagram, the measurement model in Figure 4 states that all over indicators for each variable own The outer loading / factor loading value is more than 0.7, which means all over

valid indicator. With thus, the research model has fulfil condition validity convergent which means that all over valid indicator in measure the construct.

Validity test converge also can done with look at AVE (Average Variance Extracted). It is declared that the construct meets convergent validity if the construct's AVE value is more than 0.5.

Table 2: AVE Results

Variabel	Nilai AVE (Average Variance Extracted)
Persepsi Harga	0.605
Promosi	0.546
Persepsi Produk	0.571
Brand Image	0.580
Customer Satisfaction	0.575
Repurchase Order	1.000

The table showing all over variable own AVE value is more than 0.5. so that can concluded all over variable has fulfil validity discriminant (Ghozali& Latan (2019:37).

➤ *Test result Discriminant Validity*

Validity test discriminant one of them did through the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) test. Recommended HTMT value should be smaller of 0.85 (Clark & Watson 1995; Kline 2011) while others propose smaller value of 0.90 (Gold et al. 2001; Teo et al. 2008).

Table 3: HTMT Test Results

	Brand Image	Customer Satisfaction	Persepsi Harga	Persepsi Produk	Promosi	Repurchase Intention
Brand Image						
Customer Satisfaction	0.897					
Persepsi Harga	0.711	0.756				
Persepsi Produk	0.871	0.731				
Promosi	0.769	0.795	0.700			
Repurchase Intention	0.499	0.681	0.479	0.536		

Based on the resulting HTMT test results show that all between construct own HTMT value is less from 0.90. Thus, it can be stated that all constructs are valid in terms of discriminant validity.

square root of average variance extracted (AVE) value for each construct with the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. Validity test results discriminant based on the Fornell Lackers test obtained as follows:

The discriminant validity test can also be carried out using the Fornell and Larcker method by comparing the

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker Test Results

	Brand Image	Customer Satisfaction	Persepsi Harga	Persepsi Produk	Promosi	Repurchase Intention
Brand Image	0.761					
Customer Satisfaction	0.722	0.758				
Persepsi Harga	0.593	0.608	0.778			
Persepsi Produk	0.720	0.592	0.579	0.755		
Promosi	0.559	0.580	0.456	0.515	0.766	
Repurchase Intention	0.570	0.663	0.451	0.561	0.485	0.827

The result obtained every construct own greater value rather than correlation between construct One with other constructs in models. With so, then can stated that all construct has been valid validity discriminant.

and Q-Square predictive relevance (Q²). While, level significance coefficient track used for testing hypothesis ie predict connection between latent variable.

B. *Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)*

Inner model testing can be done seen through mark coefficient determination of R-Square (R²), effect size (F²),

➤ *R-Square Value Test Results (R²)*

Coefficient determination R Square (R²) shows how much big variable exogenous explain variable its endogenous.

Table 5: R Square Value (R²)

Konstruk	R Square	R Square Adjusted	Kategori
Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	0.601	0.592	Moderat
Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.489	0.474	Moderat

Based on The R-Square value in Table 5 shows that The R-Square value of the Repurchase Intention (Y2) variable is 0.489. This value means that variability The Repurchase Intention construct can be explained by variability the construct of Customer Satisfaction, Price, Product, Promotion, Brand Image is 60.1%. This value indicates category “medium” relationship, meanwhile the rest 39.9 % is explained by other variables outside those studied. Meanwhile, the R-Square value of the Customer Satisfaction variable (Y1) is of 0.601. The R-Square value shows influence simultaneous Price, Product, Promotion ,

Brand Image towards Customer Satisfaction of 60.1% indicates category “Medium” relationship , meanwhile the rest 39.9 % is explained by other variables outside those studied .

➤ Test result Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The Q² value of the model is more than 0 , indicating that the model has good predictive relevance , whereas Q² value is less from 0 indicates the model is lacking has predictive relevance.

Table 6: Predictive Relevance Value (Q²)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Persepsi Harga	885.000	885.000	
Promosi	531.000	531.000	
Persepsi Produk	708.000	708.000	
Brand Image	885.000	885.000	
Customer Satisfaction	708.000	475.735	0.328
Repurchase Intention	354.000	246.254	0.304

Based on Test Results Communality Cross Validation of Constructs in table 6 above can seen that all variable own greater value _ from 0. With thereby so can interpreted that all variable own very strong value , where number highest that is with Q2 value = 0.304 meaning that the Intention to Use variable has mark strong and relevant predictions . _

➤ Testing Hypothesis

Testing hypothesis PLS-SEM analysis in this study used significance 5% or with tolerance error $\alpha = 0.05$. As for taking decision in PLS-SEM analysis for hypotheses with a 5% significance test is If |t-statistic| value > 1.96 or mark significance (p-value) < 0.05 and the path coefficient value is positive.

Fig 5: Path Diagram Path Coefficient & T-Statistics Structural Model (Inner Model)

Table 7: Results of Direct and Indirect Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sampel (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Values	Ket.
Persepsi Harga (X1) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	0.230	0.073	3.148	0.002	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Promosi (X2) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	0.210	0.066	3.157	0.002	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Persepsi Produk (X3) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	0.030	0.084	0.361	0.718	Tidak Berpengaruh signifikan
Brand Image (X4) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1)	0.446	0.073	6.153	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Customer Satisfaction (Y1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.469	0.116	4.048	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Persepsi Harga (X1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	-0.026	0.073	0.357	0.721	Tidak Berpengaruh signifikan
Promosi (X2) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.089	0.078	1.133	0.258	Tidak Berpengaruh signifikan
Persepsi Produk (Y3) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.229	0.083	2.755	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Brand Image (X4) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.032	0.118	0.271	0.787	Tidak Berpengaruh signifikan
Persepsi Harga (X1) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.108	0.037	2.929	0.004	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan dimediasi oleh Customer Satisfaction
Promosi (X2) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.098	0.040	2.429	0.015	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan dimediasi oleh Customer Satisfaction
Persepsi Produk (X3) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.014	0.040	0.354	0.723	Tidak berhasil memediasi
Brand Image (X4) → Customer Satisfaction (Y1) → Repurchase Intention (Y2)	0.209	0.066	3.177	0.002	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan dimediasi oleh Customer Satisfaction

V. DISCUSSION

A. H1: Effect of Price Perception on Customer Satisfaction

H1 in this study was accepted. These results are in accordance with research in line with research by Puspa Dewi (2020) which states that Price Perception has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

It is pregnant understanding that satisfaction consumer arise Because consumer perceive price A product as useful product for himself, fine from facet quality product, quality service and atmosphere and facilities at Krisbow.

B. H2: Effect of Promotion on Customer Satisfaction

H2 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Dedek Kumara (2021), which states Promotion influential positive significant towards Customer Satisfaction.

However that's good something product, if consumer Not yet Once hear it or not Certain the product will useful for them, then they No will buy it. Basically promotion is all purposeful activity communicate or convey something product to the target market to give information about privileges, uses and most importantly is about its existence, to change attitude or encourage people to act (in this thing buy). The main aim of promotion is to inform, influence and persuade and remind consumers.

C. H3: Influence Perception Product towards Customer Satisfaction

H3 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with study Rindo Olivia (2021), which states Perception Product No influential positive and not significant towards Customer Satisfaction. It means Perception Product is variables that don't influencing Customer Satisfaction at PT Krisbow. Whether the quality is good or bad is judged by consumers based on consumer

perceptions. A product is said to be of quality if it meets the needs and desires of buyers.

D. H4: Influence of Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction

H4 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Alex Santana (2019), which states that Brand Image has an influence positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction.

Distribution answer respondents for variables image brand show part respondents stated strongly agree that Krisbow own image brand from characteristic different characteristics with product other. Whereas there is a number of respondents stated No agree with brand Krisbow is famous product Because a number of consumer only use product the so that No know that product Krisbow is famous product.

E. H5: Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention

H5 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with study Sharifa Diyanti, et., al (2021), that satisfaction customer give influence positive significant against Repurchase Intention.

Result of exchange information aims to expand experience emotional customer so that make evaluation more focused customers that can be ended own interest in buying back, esp to product Krisbow. Therefore, in arrangement business, if satisfaction to product maintained from time to time, p the will willing to buy product more often. Customers who are bound by loyalty sentiments will be tied to product providers. So, things that lead to satisfaction and then end up having an interest in buying the product again. Thus, the better the customer satisfaction, the higher the level of repurchase interest, while the worse the customer satisfaction, the worse the repurchase interest level.

F. H6: Influence Price Perception on Repurchase Intention

H6 in this study was rejected. These results are consistent with research (Wijaya, 2019) where price No influential on *Repurchase Intention*. It means Price Perception is not is variables that influence Repurchase Intention at PT Krisbow. The more competitive perception consumer to price No make consumer have interest buy Again, this is because PT Krisbow customers be in the circle intermediate above and also consumers who come who really are own need to product the so that price No make influencing things consumers to buy back because A price.

G. H7: Influence Promotion on Repurchase Intention

H7 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with study Ekawati and Dewi, (2019) stated Promotion No influential on Repurchase Intention. Based on results analysis descriptive, known that on the statement When consumers know that Krisbow use good and quality ingredients in the product, this can be done create perception that product that 's better. It delivers impression

that product Krisbow own good quality so that consumers already know matter the without need see promotion what Krisbow gave.

H. H8: Influence Perception Product on Repurchase Intention

H8 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with study Yusril Ammar (2022) stated Perception Product influential positive and significant on Repurchase Intention.

Krisbow own period time resilience The product is quite old so this makes it easier consumers to measure how long is the rate resilience product that to get used. This shows that product Krisbow own good quality. It shows that the more Good Quality Product so will increase interest buy back.

I. H9: Influence Brand Image to Repurchase Intention

H9 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with research (Kusdyah, 2012) means *Brand Image* No is variables that influence Repurchase Intention. Brand Image does not own significant influence to interest buy repeat Where brand is what 's on your mind consumers and considered as A Name or the next symbol become an image. Brand Image not yet Of course become influencing factors interest buy repeat consumer.

J. H10: Influence Price Perception on Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction

H10 in this study is accepted. These results are in agreement with study RatlanPardede& Yudi Haryadi (2019) stated Price perception matters positive and significant Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction. Based on results testing hypothesis show connection satisfaction customer partial mediation on influence perception price towards Customer Satisfaction, meaning although customer No analyzed satisfaction, customer still buy product Krisbow during price offered in accordance with quality and satisfaction customer . So that can concluded the more Good price offered in accordance with quality products, customers will Repurchase the product Krisbo.

K. H11: Influence Promotion Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction

H11 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Annisa Dewiyan (2021) which states Promotion influential positive and significant Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction. Evaluation respondents to variable promotion show that respondents feel satisfied if satisfaction customer. Promotions carried out Krisbow interesting attention, interest consumers to find out more about Product Krisbow become higher after get promotion and satisfaction consumers, basically consumer evaluate promotions carried out Krisbow capable interesting desire consumer.

L. H12: Influence Perception Product Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction

H12 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with Lena Ellitan's research (2023) states Perception Product influential positive and significant Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction. This means that Customer Satisfaction is not succeed mediate Perception Product on Repurchase Intention. Quality good product is hope consumers that must be met by the company, because quality good product is key development productivity a company.

M. H13: Influence Brand Image on Repurchase Intention is mediated by Customer Satisfaction

H13 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Fitria & Fakaubun (2019) which states that image brand own influence positive significant to interest buy repeat with satisfaction customer as variable mediation. Research result show that image brand influential significant to interest buy repeat with satisfaction customer as intervening variable. Customer Krisbow owns it positive imaged something brand, will be more likely to do so purchase. With experience Good to something brand or company added good experience in the past will create satisfaction customers themselves and become reason for customers to do purchase in a way repetitive.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

Conclusions of This research is:

- Price perception matters positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction
- Promotion influential positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction
- Perception Product No influential towards Customer Satisfaction
- Brand Image is influential positive and significant towards Customer Satisfaction
- Customer Satisfaction has an effect positive and significant on Repurchase Intention
- Price Perception does not influential on Repurchase Intention
- Promotion No influential on Repurchase Intention
- Perception Product influential on Repurchase Intention
- Brand Image does not influential on Repurchase Intention
- Price perception matters positive and significant on Repurchase Intent mediated by Customer Satisfaction
- Promotion influential positive and significant on Repurchase Intent mediated by Customer Satisfaction
- Perception Product No influential on Repurchase Intent mediated by Customer Satisfaction
- Brand Image is influential positive and significant on Repurchase Intent mediated by Customer Satisfaction

B. Suggestion

- **For Companies:** In the Brand Image indicator variable product Krisbow can used for all circles Still low on the Brand Image variable so need repaired so that with exists products for all circles, then Companies can too reach all existing market share as well as Products provided Krisbow can influence interest buy back, then the advice given researcher is to continue increase quality products to increase Lots customer.
- **For Researchers Furthermore:** This research still has many shortcomings and limitations. The author suggests that further research re-examine the relationship between the direct influence of Price, Promotion, Product and Brand Image Perceptions on Customer Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention, and re-examine the indirect influence of Price, Promotion, Product and Brand Image Perceptions on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction, considering This research found that there were still positive relationships but no significant effect.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Afrilita T N. 2013. SWOT Analysis in Determining Marketing Strategy at PT. Samekarindo Indah (Nur Afrillita). E-Journal Admin. Business. 1(1):56–70.
- [2.] Arifianti R, Raharja Sun J, R. 2020. Implementation of the Dropship Strategy in the Supply Chain in the Ceramics Industry. AdBispreneur. 4(3):243.doi:10.24198/adbispreneur.v4i3.25761.
- [3.] Batu RL, Suryani NI, Septia N, Sekaryahya PF. 2020. The Influence of Price and Application Service Innovation on Decisions to Use Express Taxi Services: Survey of Express Taxis Application Downloaders. J. Nas. Manaj. Marketer. HR. 1(01):1–22.doi:10.47747/jnmpsdm.v1i01.6.
- [4.] Budi RTP. 2014. Management Modern Marketing .
- [5.] Hikmayanti H, Sri I, Rofi'i . 2016. Analysis of Factors That Influence Purchasing Decisions Telephone Handheld . J. ITENKA. 16. [downloaded 2022 Dec 21]. Available at: <https://ejurnal.poliban.ac.id/index.php/intekna/article/view/329/286>
- [6.] Imon W, Tumbel A, Mandagie Y. 2018. Analysis of Influencing Factors Success and Failure in the Marketing Strategy of Payless Shoe Store Megamall Branch. J. EMBA J. Ris. Econ. Management , Business and Accounting . 6(3):1308–1317.doi:10.35794/EMBA.V6I3.20213.
- [7.] layer . 2016. The Influence of Competitive Advantage Strategy on Behavior Consumers In Business Retail (Study at Indomaret and Alfamart , Manado). J. LPPM Bid. EkoSosBudKum . 3(2):1–13.
- [8.] Martinus B, Susanto D. 2022. The Influence of Marketing Strategy To To Increase in Sales Volume at UD Neutral in BawoOtalua Subdistrict Lahusa Regency South Nias . 1(1):1–10.
- [9.] Priangani A. 2013. Strengthening Marketing Management in Context. J. Kebangs. 2(4):1–9.

- [10.] Utomo TJ. 2016. Functions and Roles of Retail Businesses in Marketing Channels. *Econ Focus*. June. 4(1):44–55.
- [11.] Ghozali I. 2017. Ghozali, Imam. *App. Anal. Multivar. With Progr. IBM SPSS 21 Update PLS Regression*. Semarang Publishing Agency Univ. Diponegoro.
- [12.] Humannisa RL. 2020 Jan 1. The Effect Of Marketing Communication Toward Purchase Intention Of Multimedia Products From Pt. Balai Pustaka (Persero) Consumer Attitude Mediation. *Int. J. Innov. Sci. Res. Technol.* [Downloaded 2022 Oct 24]. Available at: https://Www.Academia.Edu/42191585/The_Effect_Of_Marketing_Communication_Toward_Purchase_Intention_Of_Multimedia_Products_From_Pt_Balai_Pustaka_aka_Persero_Consumer_Attitude_Mediation
- [13.] Lenaini I. 2021. Purposive and Sampling Techniques . *J. Study, Researcher . Developer . Educator . Sej.* 6(1):33–39.
- [14.] Sekaran U, Bougie R. 2016. *Research Methods For Business A Skill Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [15.] Sugiyono . 2014. *Research Methods Quantitative , Qualitative and R&D*. Alfabeta . [Downloaded 2022 Dec 6]. Available at:
- [16.] <https://Opac.Perpusnas.Go.Id/DetailOpac.aspx?Id=911046>
- [17.] Sugiyono P. 2017. *Research Methods Business : Approach Quantitative , Qualitative , Combination , and R&D*. CV. Alfabeta : Bandung.
- [18.] Gross, R. (2017). A Theoretical Consumer Decision Making Model: The Influence of Interactivity and Information Overload on Consumers Intent to Purchase Online. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*.
- [19.] Kim, J. H., Kim, M., Yoo, J., & Park, M. (2020). Consumer decision-making in a retail store: the role of mental imagery and gender differences. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [20.] Purwati, AA, Setiawan, O., Sandria, W., & Hamzah, ML (2022). RETAIL BUSINESS PURCHASE DECISION: THE ROLE OF PRODUCT QUALITY AND STORE IMAGE. *International Conference on Business & Social Sciences*.
- [21.] Rahayu, Y., & Melinda, T. (2021). THE FACTOR ANALYSIS ON PURCHASING DECISION MAKING IN STORES X. *The Fourth International Conference on Entrepreneurship*.
- [22.] Anang F. 2019. *Marketing (Basics and Concepts)*. print first, publisher Qiara Media, East Java.
- [23.] Aprianitasari . 2015. Influence Perceived Value, Perceived Price and Brand Image on Purchase Intention Store Brand Products (Case study of Super Indo Supermarket consumers in Yogyakarta). *Univ. Yogyakarta State.* (49):1–171.
- [24.] AudiahUmairah. 2019. Influence Countrt Of Origin, Brand Image And Quality Service Regarding Food Purchasing Decisions on the Grab Application at the Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra During the Covid 19 Pandemic. *J. Ilm. Univ. North Sumatra.*:1–66.
- [25.] Brama Kumbara V. 2021. Determination of Customer Value and Purchasing Decisions : Analysis Quality Products , Product Design and Endorsement. *J. Management Science. Apply.* 2(5):604–630.doi:10.31933/jimt.v2i5.568.
- [26.] Darul S, Lampung U. 2021. *Tafkirulqitshodiyah* . 01:1–9.
- [27.] Daryanto I. 2014. *Consumers and services prime*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=989096>
- [28.] Dewi NN, Wibowo R. 2018. Analysis of the Influence of Products, Price Perceptions and Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction (Case Study of Juson Home Furniture in Sidoarjo Regency). *Manag. Accounts. Res. J* 3(1):1–11.
- [29.] Dwi Wahyuni CR. 2017. Service Quality and Its Effect on Customer Loyalty Mediated by Satisfaction at Bank MuamalatJombang. *Exist J. Ris. Econ. and Business.* 12(1):69–82.doi:10.26533/eksis.v12i1.84.
- [30.] Erni Yunaida. 2017. The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty for Evalube Lubricating Oil Products in Langsa City. *J. Manaj. and Finance* . 6(2):798–807.
- [31.] Fandy T, Gregorius C. 2016. *Service, Quality & Satisfaction*. 4th volume.
- [32.] Fitra J. 2017. Promotion Strategy Sale Retail Traditional (Study of Traders Karangsembung Market Groceries). *Focus Media Business Reviewer. Manaj. and Accountant* . 16(01):65–79.doi:10.32639/focusbisnis.v16i01.81.
- [33.] Freekley SM, Sepang JL, Soegoto AS. 2018. Influence Quality Products , Prices and Quality Service To Satisfaction Consumers at Pt. Air Manado. *J. EMBA J. Ris. Econ. Management , Business and Accounting.* 6(3):1658–1667.doi:10.35794/emba.v6i3.20411.
- [34.] Hellier C, Tully V, Forrest S, Jaggard P, MacRae M, Habicht D, Greene A, Collins K. 2015. Improving multidisciplinary communication at ward board rounds using video enhanced reflective practice. *BMJ Qual. Improv. Reports.* 4(1):u206968.w2801.doi:10.1136/BMJQUALITY.U206968.W2801. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: / pmc/articles/PMC4645856/
- [35.] Humannisa RL. 2020 Jan 1. The Effect Of Marketing Communication Toward Purchase Intention Of Multimedia Products From Pt. Balai Pustaka (Persero) Consumer Attitude Mediation. *Int. J. Innov. Sci. Res. Technol.* [downloaded 2022 Oct 24]. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/42191585/The_Effect_Of_Marketing_CommunicationToward_Purchase_Intention_Of_Multimedia_Products_From_Pt_Balai_Pustaka_a_Persero_Consumer_Attitude_Mediation
- [36.] Kotler, Keller. 2018. *Management Marketing Edition 12 Volume 1*. jenniPurba , editor. PT Index .
- [37.] Kotler P. 2018. *Management marketing* / Philip Kotler, Kevin Lane Keller ; translator , Bob Sabran; editor, Adi Maulana, Wibi Hardani | OPAC National Library of the Republic of Indonesia. 16th volume.

- [downloaded 2022 Dec 16]. Available at: <https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=109678>
- [38.] Kotler P, Armstrong G. 2016. Principles Of Marketing 14Ed: Global Edition. 14th Ed. Harlow: Pearson.
- [39.] Kotler PT. 2016. Marketing management. Pearson United Kingdom.
- [40.] Lily H, Yurike V. 2015. Influence Quality Service and Price Perception _ Satisfaction Customers on Airlines Tiger Air Mandala Flights. WIDYA Ekon E-Journal. 1(2338–7807):11.
- [41.] Lupiyoadi R. 2016. Services Marketing Management: Competency Based | Faculty of Economics and Business, Brawijaya University. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <http://digilibfeb.ub.ac.id/opac/detail-opac?id=34514>
- [42.] Muharam W, Soliha E. 2017. Quality Product , Brand Image, Price Perception and Purchasing Decisions Honda Mobilio consumers. Semin. Nas. Unisbank Multi Discipline Sciences 2017. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <https://www.neliti.com/id/publications/172666/>
- [43.] Peter JP. 2000. Consumer behavior: consumer behavior and marketing strategy. Volume 2 / J. Paul Peter; Jerry C. Olson; translated by Damos Sihombing. Erlangga.
- [44.] Peter JP. 2013. Consumer behavior and marketing strategy. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <https://lib.ui.ac.id>
- [45.] Rachmawati KD, Patrikha FD. 2021. Influence Diversity Products and Promotions to decision purchases at Pesen Kopi Bojonegoro City During the Covid 19 Pandemic . J. Educator. Econ. J. Ilm. Educational Sciences, Economic Sciences. and Social Sciences. 15(2):182–189.doi:10.19184/jpe.v15i2.24590.
- [46.] Rivai AR, Wahyudi TA. 2017. The Influence of Quality Perceptions, Brand Image, Price Perceptions on Customer Loyalty with Trust and Customer Satisfaction as Mediating Variables. Media Discourse Partners. 4(1):29–37.
- [47.] Sagala R. 2019. The Influence of Perceptions of Quality, Price, Company Reputation and Customer Satisfaction on Decision Making to Purchase Lion Air Flight Services at Pt. Vina Tour & Travel Medan. J. Manaj. and Business.:205–225.doi:10.54367/ jmb.v17i2.415.
- [48.] Schiffman LG, Kanuk LL. 2015. Consumer behavior. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [49.] Supriyadi, Fristin Y, KN GI. 2016. Influence Quality Product and Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions (Study on Students User Brand Shoe Products. J. Business and Management. 3(1):135–144.
- [50.] Swasty W. 2016. Branding: understand and design brand strategy / WiraniaSwasty | Blitar City Library and Archives Service. Teen PT Rosdakary. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <http://inlislite.blitarkota.go.id/opac/detail-opac?id=10490>
- [51.] Thamrin A, Tantri F. 2019. Marketing Management. PT. Raja GrafindoPersada. [downloaded 2022 Dec 19]. Available at: <https://repo.pelitabangsa.ac.id/xmlui/handle/123456789/1498>.